

Deliverable 8.1. Learning Objectives for training on IEA

WP 8 Building Capacity for the IEA
Deliverable 8.1.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Mission Atlantic project aims to develop and apply Integrated Ecosystem Assessments (IEAs) in the Atlantic Ocean. Capacity building is an important part of facilitating IEA at the Atlantic scale, and specific capacity building needs will differ depending on the context where IEA will be applied. The Mission Atlantic project, in order to address this need, will develop on-line learning modules to support capacity building in response to the needs of stakeholders.

Mission Atlantic carried out an external survey (led by WMU) and a workshop (led by ICES) to identify learning objectives for on-line learning that would be needed to support each part of the IEA process, also including any cross cutting skills needed for all parts of the process. The learning objectives will serve to build on line training materials for key IEAs target audiences: researchers, marine resource managers and policy/decision makers in the Mission Atlantic project.

The on-line survey and the workshop targeted respondents who had experience with, and were knowledgeable about, IEA. The respondents for the survey were selected using purposive sampling, and effort was made to achieve balanced representation in the geography, disciplines, career stages and “voices” (e.g. user of the sea, manager, NGO representative, researcher, etc) of the participants. The survey was run on-line from June-September 2021. The survey asked the stakeholders to identify the skill sets needed to support the delivery of IEA in the Atlantic region, and also served as a way to invite participants to sign up for the workshop. The results of the survey were summarized and then used to develop reference sheets. These reference sheets served as background information to trigger discussion during the workshop to support the development of concrete learning objectives for on-line learning. A second survey for internal Mission Atlantic participants was also conducted (led by USP). The purpose of this survey was to identify the internal expertise within the project so that it could later be matched with training needs to develop e-learning later in the Mission Atlantic project.

On 23 November 2021, ICES hosted a workshop on zoom to convene stakeholders to further develop concrete learning objectives for on-line learning. 31 participants joined the workshop, which was facilitated by 4 Mission Atlantic scientists. The participants worked in break out groups which each focused on the development of learning objectives for a different step in the IEA process. Each breakout group was provided with reference sheets as background material to start the discussion. The reference sheets were compiled from the on-line survey. Each breakout group delivered lists of important foundational and IEA step-specific skills, along with learning objectives. Where necessary, the learning objectives delivered by each breakout group were refined by two of the workshop facilitators to align with Bloom’s taxonomy for defining learning objectives. These facilitators also inferred the target audience as either researchers, marine resource managers and policy/decision makers as needed. The participants noted a large number of discipline specific, and cross-disciplinary skills needed to support each part of the IEA process. It was recognised that knowledge of the IEA cycle alone and technical or scientific skills to support parts of it are insufficient to effectively implement the entire IEA process. The IEA process also requires skills to work and to communicate effectively across sectors, disciplines and with decision makers. There is no such thing as a one-size-fits-all solution for capacity building, and this will always need to be tuned to the specific needs of any given context.

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1. Mission Atlantic Background

MISSION ATLANTIC develops and systematically applies Integrated Ecosystem Assessments (IEAs) in the Atlantic Ocean. IEAs enable identification of ecosystem components most at risk from natural hazards and the consequences of human activities. The project employs all available information on those sources, the pressures they impose and the ecosystem components that are affected, to identify the most important risk factors for sustainable development of the Atlantic Ocean. MISSION ATLANTIC develops and tests high-resolution numerical ocean ecosystem models, as well as employing advanced statistical approaches, artificial neural networks, and risk assessment methods in support of the IEA cycle. Cross-Atlantic seagoing activities will collect new observations on the shelf and open ocean, across benthic and pelagic biomes, to validate ecosystem models and explore the biogeography of plankton and fish communities. Advanced combinations of marine robotic solutions and acoustic sensors are further developed and deployed to provide new data and to deliver the next generation of autonomous systems in support of IEAs.

MISSION ATLANTIC aims at supporting the “All Atlantic Ocean research alliance” and the implementation of the Galway and Belem statements. In 2017, the European Union, South Africa and Brazil co-signed the [Belém statement](#) on Atlantic Research and Innovation Cooperation for the South and tropical Atlantic and Southern Ocean. Following the Galway Statement, which focuses on North-Atlantic cooperation, the Belém statement furthers the integrated approach to research and development across the whole Atlantic Ocean and its bordering countries.

1.1 The role of this deliverable

One of the goals of the Mission Atlantic project is to build future capacity on IEA topics. This report aims at informing the providers of teaching output in WP1-7 about end-user needs to shape the online training under WP8. It also delivers Learning Objectives addressed to key IEAs target audiences: researchers, marine resource managers and policy/decision makers for on-line learning.

1.2 Interaction with the All-Atlantic Community

This task benefitted from collaboration with the AANCHOR project, particularly interaction with the All-Atlantic community. Mission Atlantic WP8 has interacted with the All Atlantic community in education initiatives such as the ICES led WGEDU and AANCHOR WP3 on Capacity Building. Moreover, All Atlantic Youth Ambassadors participated in our external survey, and were invited to the workshop. Anchor project WP3 on Capacity building organized about 5 meetings to delineate a joint action. Mission Atlantic, represented by Mary Gasalla and Mary Wisz participated in these meetings and endeavoured to link Mission Atlantic’s capacity building work with AANCHOR. In the future Mission Atlantic can provide expertise on learning objectives that align with the aims of the proposed Join Action and the 6 thematic areas, i.e. climate variability, ocean observation, ocean resources, ocean technology, emerging pollutants and polar research.

1.3 Contributors to this deliverable

The learning objectives were compiled through a combination of an on-line survey of stakeholders external to the Mission Atlantic project developed and administered by WMU during the summer of 2021, and a workshop led by ICES in collaboration with WMU in November of 2021. The University of Sao Paulo (USP) also engaged actively with WMU and ICES in both the survey and workshop idealization and planning. The Learning Objectives will structure the Mission Atlantic on-line training programme in Task 8.2 based on key project outputs. A survey of Mission Atlantic internal participants

was also carried out by USP and WMU to identify the initial expertise within the Mission Atlantic WPs that can be called upon to deliver E-learning later in the Mission Atlantic project during task 8.2 and other capacity building initiatives. The internal survey is introduced here, but will not be analyzed in this report because it will be the subject of future work in Mission Atlantic. This report was prepared by WMU, USP and ICES with contributions from DTU, IMR, UBH, UPO.

2. Survey on skill sets (External participants)

WMU led a detailed on-line survey containing open ended questions to identify skills sets needed to support the development and uptake of IEAs. Surveys were used *in lieu* of face- to- face interviews in order to cast a wide net to inventory stakeholder capacity building needs, and to increase access to as many relevant external stakeholders as possible during the pandemic.

Respondents were selected by a process of purposive sampling (non-probability form of sampling), as the goal was to sample participants who were knowledgeable of the IEA approach (or steps of it) on a theoretical and/or practical level. An initial list of survey participants was derived from personal and professional contacts provided by the Case Study leaders of the MISSION ATLANTIC project. Respondents were selected by a process of purposive sampling as the goal was to sample participants which were relevant to the research questions that are posed (Bryman, A. 2016). The survey reached participants via the ICES network of 5000 scientists, MISSION ATLANTIC case study leads, and key partners such as the All Atlantic Research Alliance Youth Ambassadors via a snowball approach. The survey was distributed in batches (as Case Study leaders were providing the contact information); The survey ran from 9 June to 14 September 2021.

The survey was anonymous (although participants could include their contact information if they wished to be contacted to participate in the workshop). Prior to circulation, the survey was submitted and approved by the WMU ethics committee on 9 June 2021. The survey questions are included in [Appendix 1](#). The questions asked about the participants' role in their organisation, and their suggestions for training needs for each part of the IEA cycle. They were also asked to supply learning objectives for on-line learning. Stakeholders who completed the survey were also asked if they would participate in a workshop hosted by ICES (workshop details below) to identify learning objectives for Integrated Ecosystem Assessments (IEAs) and the online training program in MISSION ATLANTIC .

By the time the survey was closed on 14 September, 32 survey responses were collected and analysed. 19 were members of research/academia (15 from Natural science, 4 from social sciences), 2 members were from environmental non-governmental organizations, 2 identified themselves as “managers”, 6 identified themselves as from the Advisory sector, and 2 were “users of the sea”.

The results of the survey were summarized to develop reference sheets of background information during the workshop, and to help inform the development of learning objectives by workshop participants. These summary reference sheets are presented in [Appendix 2](#).

3. Survey on expertise (internal Mission Atlantic partners)

In order to identify the training capacity within the Mission Atlantic consortium, University of São Paulo in collaboration with WMU developed a survey for internal Mission Atlantic partners, initially focused at the Work Package lead (WP) level. The survey occurred from 15/09 to 14/10/2021 and results will be used later in the Mission Atlantic project to help identify a match between learning objectives for Mission Atlantic online training and capacity within the project to deliver on those topics. Consortium's WP leads were asked to respond to an exploratory online survey regarding (1) expertise available to capacity building; (2) ability to prepare training; (3) emerging ideas and topics for e-learning and training courses; (4) willingness to prepare material and deliver courses; (5) interest to attend the WP8 workshop on training objectives

4. Mission Atlantic WP8 workshop on training objectives

ICES organised and held a workshop in close collaboration with WMU and USP that was held on 23 November 2021 to consult ocean stakeholders from industry, policy makers and academia to identify IEA training needs and learning objectives relevant for maritime and ocean practitioners. The discussions were pre-supplemented with information stemming from some of the Mission Atlantic stakeholder surveys (with T9.2.2) and during WP1 regional CS stakeholder workshops.

As with the external survey, the workshop organizers aimed for a balanced representation in terms of geographical area, academic background, and voices (e.g. user of the sea, manager, NGO, researcher). Selection for the workshop was based on a balance of expertise, geographical spread, and considered knowledgeable of the IEA approach on a theoretical and or practical level. Some of the participants were identified from those who expressed interest and who shared their contact details via the online survey of stakeholders external to the project. Others were identified through the Mission Atlantic case study leads and the ICES network. The list of workshop participants, including their background, and geographical area where they have worked on IEA (as a whole or elements of it) can be seen in section 7. Workshop participants were assigned to one of 6 breakout groups. Each breakout group was assigned a step IEA process (Figure 1): 1) Define goals and targets 2) Develop indicators 3) Assess Ecosystem 4) Analyse uncertainty and Risk 5) Evaluate Strategies 6) Implement monitor and evaluate action. Members of the breakout groups were assigned based on their expertise on a particular part of the cycle and effort was made to balance geographic, gender and discipline diversity to the best degree possible.

Define Goals and Targets: scoping process to identify key management goals and targets.

Develop Indicators: identify appropriate indicators of key components in an ecosystem; allows change to be measured.

Assess Ecosystem: evaluate overall ecosystem status and trends relative to management goals and targets.

Analyse Uncertainty & Risk: evaluate risk to the ecosystem posed by human activities and natural processes; measured through the risk to indicators.

Evaluate Strategies: evaluate potential for success in reaching goals and targets; evaluate potential for different management strategies; uses management strategy evaluation (MSE); trade-offs are considered.

Implementing, monitoring, and evaluating action: (inner circle); based on the MSE, an action is selected and implemented; monitoring indicators will help determine if the action is successful.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the IEA framework (Figure from Samhouri et al., 2014 Levin et al., 2009; Dickey-Collas 2014; Samhouri et al., 2014; Levin et al., 2014; Harvey et al., 2017). Each workshop participant was assigned to a breakout group to develop learning objectives and skills for one step of the IIEA process.

Information reference sheets (based on external survey results- Appendix 2) were provided to the breakout groups prior the workshop were draft descriptions of the content and learning objectives for the modules on “Defining goals and targets”, “Developing indicators”, “Assessing the ecosystem”, “Analysis of uncertainty and risk”, “Evaluating strategies”, and “Implementing, monitoring, and evaluating action” were included. The reference sheets also gave a list of potential courses / topics that could be covered to reach such learning objectives. Workshop participants were asked to revise, as a group, the text included in the reference sheets and to suggest changes or additions as required.

Each breakout group was asked to provide the following (i) learning objectives for each of the IEA E-learning modules; and (ii) lists of potential topics that could be covered in E-learning modules.

Learning objectives can be classified according to the complexity and their specificity (Adams 2015). Higher level learning objectives “require higher levels of cognitive skills and, therefore, lead to deeper learning and transfer of knowledge and skills to a greater variety of tasks and contexts” (Adams 2015). Objectives such as “to understand” or “to learn about” are considered lacking in specificity and are not suitable for designing effective learning materials. Examples of low level learning objectives are “to recognize” or “to list”, and can be used in only a limited number of applications. Higher level learning objectives such as to analyze...,to assess.. or to prioritize... can be operationalized and applied to a wider range of contexts. The learning objectives formulated by the survey and workshop participants needed to be rephrased to clearly state the higher level learning objectives according to Bloom’s taxonomy.

Not all of the learning objectives obtained from the workshop participants were phrased as specific higher level objectives according to Bloom’s taxonomy. In cases where the learning objectives required refining, they were refined by two of the workshop facilitators. Dr. W. Wawrzynski is an expert on IEA process and ICES officer) and Prof. M. S. Wisz is an expert on the IEA process and with years of experience in cross disciplinary capacity building for ocean and maritime professionals, natural scientists, social scientists, practitioners and diplomats in higher education. Mission Atlantic had 3 target learning audiences (researchers, marine resource managers and policy/decision makers)

and these were also inferred from the workshop materials and denoted as follows: researchers, marine resource managers (MRM) and policy/decision makers (PDM).

5. Results from the workshop

The workshop had strong participation and contribution from participants that discussed the external survey's results and provided comments and reflections on capacity building needs for IEA application. Information compiled here will provide a basis for an overarching IEA course composed of six modules, one module per IEA step (Figure 1), and each module having a specific set of learning objectives.

Two types of results were obtained from the workshop: (i) learning objectives for each of the IEA E-learning modules; and (ii) lists of potential courses/topics that could be covered in the IEA E-learning modules.

Below is a summary of how the final text for both sets of results after the suggested comments/additions were edited by the workshop organisers.

5.1 Learning objectives for each IEA module

IEA Module 1 on Defining goals and targets

Target learning audience:

R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Key task to be performed: Define the operational objectives that will guide the IEA cycle. Objectives are derived both from policy documents and from stakeholders' values and interests. Previous to this, key stakeholders and their specific contextual area needs have been identified.

Important considerations:

As political priorities and stakeholder' values change, so does the need to update the objectives. Official objectives constitute a frame, but one that can be challenged/debated. Local processes have more granularity/level of detail, and there will be room for a continuous and transparent processing of the various priorities within the overarching official objectives.

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Explain the IEA process including the identification of potential strengths and challenges
- Define tools and approaches to: identify, involve and maintain, participants in the IEA process R, MRM, PDM
- Apply several methods to extract objectives from policy documents, and weigh the pros and cons of each of these methods (R, MRM, PDM)

IEA Module 2 on Developing indicators

Target learning audience:

R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Key task to be performed: Identify and apply appropriate indicators of key components in an ecosystem, allowing changes to be measured.

Important considerations:

A range of skills from different fields of expertise would be needed to understand, develop, and apply indicators. Skills will be needed in the discipline an indicator is covering. For each category of indicators (e.g ecological, economic, social, institutional) there will be specific indicators. For example, indicators will be of

an ecological nature (e.g. covering the relevant aspects of ecosystem structure, function and dynamics) and also economic (e.g. value ecosystem services), social (e.g. recreational activities, recreational fisheries, people well-being) and institutional nature (e.g. framework). Some of the indicators will address several categories. Indicators will need to be tailored to the case study.

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Explain methods to develop quantitative and qualitative indicators with stakeholders and managers in support of the IEA framework (R, MRM)
- Select and apply appropriate indicators for specific IEA objectives and estimate the uncertainties associated with these (R, MRM)
- Use methods to identify indicator thresholds and reference points for ecosystem assessment (R,MRM)

IEA Module 3 on Assessing the ecosystems

Target learning audience:

R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Key task to be performed: Identify the key components and pressures on the ecosystem. Evaluate the ecosystem status and trends relative to the operational objectives defined in step 1 (Define goals and targets).

Important Considerations:

In some situations the practitioner will need to recognize or assess habitats/ecosystem in data poor areas

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Apply a range of methods to identify key components and pressures in an ecosystem, taking into consideration the strengths and weaknesses of these methods. (R, MRM)
- Compile relevant data and information to support ecosystem assessment in a particular area of interest. (R, MRM)
- Limit and bound the assessment to relevant ecosystem components and pressures. (R, MRM)
- Apply tools to detect trends in spatial and temporal data. (e.g. GIS / time series analytics) (R, MRM)

IEA Module 4 on Analysis of uncertainty and risk

Target learning audience:

R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Key task to be performed: Evaluate the risks to the ecosystem posed by human activities and natural processes (i.e, risk that indicators from step 2 will fall below the operational objectives defined in step 1).

Important considerations:

Usually, a qualitative assessment of risks would be undertaken first (a screening out of low-risk activities); this will be followed by a detailed assessment (often quantitative). Carrying out this task, closely related to step 3 (Assessment of the ecosystem), requires having knowledge and understanding of the concepts of uncertainty and risks, its tools, and methods of analysis. Such is the topic of the current module

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Explain concepts of risk and uncertainty
- Use assessments of uncertainty and risk to inform decisions (MRM, PDM)
- Apply methods and tools for risk assessment, (e.g. ODEMM), taking into consideration their strengths and weaknesses (R, MRM)

IEA Module 5 on Evaluating strategies

Target learning audience:

R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Key task to be performed: Evaluate the potential of different management strategies to successfully help reach the operational objectives defined in step 1 (Define goals and targets).

Important considerations

In this step models are used to simulate the behaviour of humans acting in and on ecosystems, as well as to simulate the ecological and environmental responses. Numerical models can be used to forecast changes in ecosystem state as a consequence of management scenarios and decision rules. They will allow for comparison of alternative strategies and potential exploration of trade-offs. This step requires that clear and operationalised objectives (from step 1) have been incorporated into clearly defined management and ecological scenarios. i.e behavioural, economic and social model. It would also require indicators that link to those objectives (from step 2, e.g. pillars of sustainability: governance, social, economic, ecological), and the understanding of context dependent factors (incl. governance, power, current economic situation). Multi-disciplinary teams - including specialists in governance structures when providing recommendations, and in science-to-policy communication, would be an asset to be part of this step. Finally, the IEA practitioner needs to be aware of the difference between advice and advocacy.

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Explain and apply management strategy evaluation approaches to achieve sustainable use of marine resources and habitats (R, MRM)
- Apply best practice for management processes and associated institutional architecture to support ecosystem management (R, MRM, PDM)
- Develop scenarios for IEA using a diversity of approaches (R, MRM)

IEA Module 6 on Implement, monitor, and evaluate action

Target learning audience:

R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Key task to be performed: Monitoring and evaluation of the management strategy implemented, and which resulted from step 5 (Evaluate strategies)

Important considerations:

A key aspect is to learn from failure, but also from success, adjusting actions for the next IEA cycle.

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Explain and apply methods to monitor the success of a management strategy, taking into consideration the strengths and weaknesses of each. (RM, PDM)
- Develop criteria to assess the effectiveness of a management strategy (e.g. achievement of operational objectives, institutional support, solving the problem in question, congruence with stakeholders perceptions). (R, MRM, PDM)

One of the groups made a comment on the need to regularly update the courses.

Further to this several of the groups suggested learning objectives for cross cutting skills that could relate to the entire IEA process. This course could be a short course researchers and marine resource managers, but most well suited for Policy and Decision makers

Cross cutting IEA skills
 Target learning audience:
 R = Researchers/Academics, MRM=Marine Resource Managers, PDM= Policy Decision makers

Important considerations:
 An overview of the IEA process, and how to implement it in practice

Learning objectives:

After completing this module, the IEA practitioner will be able to:

- Explain the steps in the IEA process
- Apply skills to effectively communicate IEA to non-specialists (R, MRM)
- Manage an IEA project (R, MRM)
- Manage stakeholders in the IEA process (R, MRM)
- Adapt and build institutions to support IEA (MRM, PDM)
- Engage one's institution with the IEA process (MRM, PDM)
- Support a transboundary IEA process (MRM, PDM)
- Communicate across teams, sectors and disciplines to support the IEA process. (R, MRM, PDM)
- Strengthen international negotiations with IEA, and vice versa. (MRM, PDM)

5.2 Suggested courses/topics to be covered in the IEA modules

Two categories of courses could be identified from the answers provided in the survey and which were confirmed during the workshop. The categories refer to *Foundations*, and *IEA-step specific*. Each category has a suggested collection of courses. The content of the course can be described by the keywords that were collected from the survey and complemented by workshop participants. Foundation courses provide the basic knowledge and concepts that will allow IEA practitioners to start working across disciplines.

It should be noted that few if any IEA experts have experience with all of these skills, even at a foundational level. It is our perception that an in-depth knowledge of all disciplines and topics involved in the operational implementation of IEA would be hard to achieve by a single person, however practitioners should be at least exposed to all the relevant concepts (breadth).

Course themes(as suggested by the workshop organizers)	Keywords and sentences (as provided as part of the survey responses and complemented by workshop participants)
<p>Foundations This category of courses provides basic knowledge and concepts which will allow IEA practitioners to start building bridges and work across disciplines “<i>effectively communicating the concepts of a familiar discipline and comprehending the concepts of unfamiliar disciplines</i>” [survey respondent # 4].</p>	
<p>Foundation of marine ecosystems</p>	<p>Biology; Marine ecology; Systems Ecology; System dynamics; Specific ecological knowledge about the ecosystem components involved in the assessment; Understanding of the ecology of an ecosystem coupled with the understanding of how pressures affect that ecosystem; Ecosystem understanding; Population dynamics; Assessment of condition and health; Introduction to dynamic ocean management;</p>

	Physical and Biological Oceanography; Ecosystem dynamics, response of ecosystems to global changes (including climate change); What is ecosystem health? (how to define it, how to measure it, link to the societal demand); Practical understanding of marine ecosystem processes and how they relate to the functioning of a healthy ecosystem
Foundations of social science	Philosophy of science; Social science; Post-normal science; Sociology; Anthropology; Health of human society; cultural and religious value; cultural and religious value systems; Ethics.
Foundations of economics	Resource economics; country/state economy; Blue economy; marine and maritime economics
Foundations of marine legislation	Policy, Marine policy; Institutions; Political science; Practitioners across the science-policy interface; Basic law of the sea; Relationship between international/regional/national/subnational law.
Human activities at sea	Benefits and risks associated to human activities at sea (fisheries, mariculture, shipping; offshore energy, oil and gas, mineral extraction, tourism, recreation deep sea mining). Ecologic, social, economic, and institutional indicators across marine industries; Foundations of stock assessment; How these industries are rapidly changing; Coastal management
Management of natural resources	EBM, EAM, Ecosystem based knowledge, ecosystem services; training on ecosystem based management (most of people think they know it, but they don't); researchers/practitioners to develop a deeper understanding of the communities that use and reside close to resources, as well as the reasons why certain ideas or traditions persist; Knowledge of the use and importance of the resource for traditional communities, SDG for justice and equality.
Facilitation, Communications, and leadership	Facilitation of meetings; Engagement processes; Leadership skills; Recognition of power dynamics; Consensus building; Negotiation; Prioritization; Structured decision-making; Co-design; co-creation; Conflict resolution; Planning and time management; how to collaborate. The IEA Team (not practitioner) needs to be able to identify and engage with stakeholders, leverage data, knowledge, and information from organisations, industry, government, researchers, and communicate across disciplines (fisheries, climate, habitat, ecosystem)
Research methods	Research skills, How to define relevant scientific research questions; Literature review skills; Knowledge of inference; Survey methodologies and design; Meta-analysis tools; Experimental design; Monitoring skills for various taxa; Field work, Surveying; Science communication; Conceptual mapping. mixed methods research, stakeholder engagement Scenario planning; . Time Management.
IT skills	Coding; R or python or other programming language; GIS, big data (i.e. climate change and oceanographic data sets); Shiny interfaces (science-policy dialogues)
IEA-step specific This category relates to courses that signal a required specialization associated to one or several of the IEA steps	
Statistics	Statistics (multivariate, nonlinear, spatial, time-series, etc.); Statistical analysis; Statistical understanding of pressure-response relationships and thresholds; Bayesian methods; Statistics incl. those associated with risk and uncertainty analyses; Statistical skills to model potential risks against indicators while controlling for confounding factors
Modelling	Computer programming; Training in modelling; Ecosystem modelling; Multivariate modelling; General introduction to IA tools and models; How to use ecosystem models; Ecopath and Ecosim models; interpretation [of models]; Simulation modelling; Scenario simulation, , Forecasting methods, Ecological modelling; Coupling bio-economic models with global circulation models (scenarios); incorporation of ecological indicators into ecosystem models; Achieve knowledge of different modelling and evaluation techniques. Communicating model outputs/uncertainty.

Data management and analysis	Data analysis; Data management; How to integrate various types and quantities of data and indicators; Indicator analysis; data/indicator aggregation; Methods for indicator aggregation; data and indicator aggregation-approaches, challenges, outcomes; Multidisciplinary analysis; time series assessment & climate change considerations, Trend analysis; time-series analysis (e.g. temporal auto-correlation); Data access and transparency (public access).
Management Strategy Evaluation	Using ecological modelling in an MSE process to determine tradeoffs and bounds of uncertainty in predictions

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The results of the external survey and the workshop highlight the diversity of skills and disciplines that are needed to support the IEA process. No single practitioner could be expected to master all of these skills. Thus, in addition to specialist and cross cutting skills, work in IEA will require the ability to communicate effectively and to work across teams, disciplines, jurisdictions, cultures, sectors and institutional levels. Although discipline specialists will always be needed, individuals having a suite of cross disciplinary skills will be better positioned to support practitioners to achieve IEA goals in practice. Knowledge of the IEA cycle alone and technical or scientific skills to support parts of it are insufficient to effectively implement the entire IEA process, which requires skills to work across sectors, disciplines and with decision makers. This list of learning objectives is not exhaustive and summarizes the viewpoints of participants with whom we could engage in this survey and workshop, most of whom were natural scientists. There is no such thing as a one-size-fits-all solution for capacity building, and this will need to be tuned to the specific needs of any given context. A wider pool of stakeholders and representatives from more disciplines would draw upon a broader pool of experiences and might expand the list of learning objectives.

The list of learning objectives did need to be refined from the material provided by the workshop participants, as the participants were asked to work under a tight time constraint. Future work will include validation of the learning objectives with the workshop participants in time to develop E-learning material.

This list provides the overview of the learning objectives and skill sets currently recognised by the stakeholders we could reach. Over time, the skills needed to support IEA can be expected to evolve. A number of the learning objectives proposed by the stakeholders can be taught by Mission Atlantic researchers. However, some of them may require skills from outside Mission Atlantic. Some of these skills concern bridging science to policy and how decision makers can better engage with and support the success of IEA. It may be that very few (if any) IEA practitioners have these skills (yet), and that it may be necessary to develop research expertise in these areas to increase the potential for uptake and use of IEA by decision makers and wider society.

7. List of participants

Tables below specify how the breakout groups were formed before the workshop. Group formation was based on the preference indicated by participants in their registration form, at the same time then aiming for a balanced representation in terms of geographical area, discipline, and representing voice. Some attendees had to cancel their workshop participation due to personal circumstances or indicated having connection problems during the event and had to leave. These persons are indicated with a: “(*)”. The lists of workshop participants (both present at plenary and at the breakout groups) were obtained from the list of login sessions registered under the Zoom call.

List of participants for Group # 1 : Define goals and targets		
Margaret (Peg) Brady	North america	Fisheries, Offshore renewable, Program coordinator; Natural sciences, Federal government agency;
Adelbert De Clercq	Europe	Humanities and social science; Natural science
David Langlet	Europe	Applied sciences
Gabriela (Gaby) Sardinha	South America	Recreation and tourism; Humanities and social science; Natural science; Applied sciences
List of participants for Group # 2 : Define goals and targets		
Kaylee Smit	Africa,	Natural science; Applied sciences
Yolanda Arjona	North Atlantic (BNJ), Europe	Fisheries, offshore renewable, offshore non-renewable; Advisory
Angel Borja	Europe; Caspian Sea, Persian Gulf	Fisheries, mariculture, offshore renewable, offshore non-renewable, shipping; Natural Sciences
Vicente Gomes	South America; South Atlantic (BNJ); Antarctic	Mariculture; Ecophysiology, Biomarkers, Pollution; Natural science; Biological Oceanography
Carlos Ferrerira(*)	South America;	Fisheries; Natural sciences; Academia
Susan Grose	Global;	Fisheries; Natural sciences
Gwendal Le Fol(*)	Global;	Fisheries; Researcher; Manager observer; Natural science; Geography
List of participants for Group # 3 : Assessing the ecosystem		
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Lucie Buttay	Europe	Fisheries; Natural sciences
Jarbas Bonetti	South America; South Atlantic (BNJ)	Natural science;
Serge Michel Garcia	Europa, Africa, Global	Fisheries; manager; Natural sciences; Fishery science; NGO; Advisory
Tânia Pereira	Europe	Natural science;
Henrique Amato Peres	South Atlantic (BNJ)	Fisheries; Natural sciences
Thomas Furey	Europe	Seabed mapping; oceanography; ecosystem modelling
List of participants for Group # 4 Analysis of uncertainty and risk		
Kelly Ortega	Africa	Fisheries; natural science
Lis Lindal Jørgensen	Arctic, Barents sea	Fisheries; shipping; natural science
Octavio Marin(*)	Europe	Shipping; Administration; Applied sciences; Public administration, Social work, Military Sciences
Michael Rust	North America	Mariculture; Coordination
List of participants for Group # 5: Define goals and targets		
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Debbi Pedreschi	Europe	Fisheries; Humanities and social science; Natural sciences; Advisory
Jemma Lonsdale(*)	Europe	Offshore renewable, oil & gas; Licensing, Manager; Natural science; Regulatory advice; Government agency
Mary Gasalla	South America, South Atlantic (BNJ);	Fisheries, Oceanography; Humanities and social science; Natural science, Advisory
List of participants for Group # 6: Implementing, monitoring, and evaluating action		
Lynne Shannon	Africa	Fisheries, Natural science, NGO, Advisory
Arina Motova	Europe	Fisheries, Manager, Humanities and social science, NGO, Advisory
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Wojciech Wawrzynski	ICES	Science Manager; Humanities and social science
Paulina Ramírez-Monsalve	WMU	Multi-users of the sea; Marine Spatial Planning; Humanities and social science; Applied sciences
Alondra Rodríguez Sofía	ICES	Human and social science
Mary S. Wisz	WMU	Cross disciplinary marine science: spatial ecology, human impacts, and future oceans

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Appendix 1. Link to the [online survey questions for external stakeholders](#), and description of survey design

Appendix 2. Link to [online survey results](#) summarized as reference sheets (aka “pagers”) of background information that were shared with workshop participants during the ICES workshop on 23 November 2021. Each reference sheet (pager) corresponds to a step in the IEA process.